

TOWARDS PHYSICAL IMPAIRMENT AWARE SOFTWARE-DEFINED PARTIALLY DISAGGREGATED NETWORKS

Arturo Mayoral Lopez-de-Lerma¹, Victor López^{2*}, Oscar Gonzalez de Dios², Andrea Campanella³, Rafał Szwedowski⁴, Konrad Mrówka⁴, Dominique Verchere⁵, Lubo Tancevski⁶, Alessio Giorgetti⁷, Ramón Casellas⁸, Hiroki Okui⁹, Juan-Pedro Fernandez Palacios²

¹Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Spain

²Telefónica I+D/Global CTO, Spain

³Open Networking Foundation, Menlo Park, USA

⁴ADVA Optical Networking, Gdynia, Poland⁵Nokia Bell-Labs, France

⁶Nokia, Germany

⁷Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna / CNIT, Pisa, Italy,

⁸CTTC/CERCA, Castelldefels, Spain

⁹NTT Communications, Tokyo, Japan

*victor.lopezalvarez@telefonica.com

Keywords: SDN, Optical disaggregation, OpenConfig, TAPI.

Abstract

Partially disaggregated networks require physical layer information to validate end-to-end characterization of WDM signals' integrity. Transport-API 2.1 includes the photonic-media layer characterization, enabling external wavelength provisioning over an Open Line System. This work presents the first proof-of-concept on a disaggregated multi-vendor testbed with TAPI 2.1.

1 Introduction

There is a great interest around the disaggregation of hardware and software components in the networking community. Such approach enables flexibility to deploy advance solutions and achieves efficiency and cost reduction within certain network scenarios. Network operators have paid attention to this technological evolution, because it can help to maintain the margin as the revenues are decreasing [1]. The deployment in optical network, following the traditional schemas, is based on end-to-end solutions where there is no interoperability of the optical components. Disaggregation enables to mix solutions from different partners to have a completer design that copes with the needs of each scenario. While the disaggregation enables create ad-hoc solution, it fragments the complexity of the system. The recent advances of Software Defined Network (SDN) allow having a common view of the network elements, so the network operators can have an end-to-end optical channel design. SDN solutions enable network operators to deploy different hardware components but still have a common view of the network elements. This enables mixing of network elements from different vendors to deploy network infrastructures. There are different scenarios demonstrating such concept in packet/optical networks like in [2, 3]. The authors in [4] presented the concept of Software Defined Transport Network (SDTN) architecture, which is depicted in Fig.1. The SDTN architecture is based on the concept of hierarchical orchestration, where each switching technology is managed by an SDN controller (SDNc).

Optical networks are the basis of the Telecommunications Operators (TELCOs) transport infrastructure in the different aggregation network domains (metropolitan, regional and long-haul). TELCOs deploy in the different aggregation domains the solution from a single vendor. The reasons behind this choice are the complexity of connectivity service provisioning in optical networking, the low-level interoperability requirements and the increase of maintenance activities. This paper demonstrates for the first time a software-defined disaggregated multi-vendor testbed with TAPI 2.1 service data model. The utilization of TAPI 2.1 enables the validation of external wavelengths into an Open Line System (OLS).

Fig. 1 Software Defined Transport Network architecture

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Info
16.544853	ONOS Controller	ADVA OLS Controller	HTTP	GET /restconf/data/tapi-common:context HTTP/1.1
16.796146	ADVA OLS Controller	ONOS Controller	HTTP	HTTP/1.1 200 OK (application/yang-data+json)
17.678362	ONOS Controller	NOKIA OT-1	TCP	48914 → 830 [PSH, ACK] Seq=1 Ack=1 Win=1780 Len=676
17.678782	NOKIA OT-1	ONOS Controller	TCP	830 → 48914 [ACK] Seq=1 Ack=677 Win=490 Len=0
17.678854	ONOS Controller	NOKIA OT-2	TCP	36122 → 830 [PSH, ACK] Seq=1 Ack=1 Win=1941 Len=676
17.679262	NOKIA OT-2	ONOS Controller	TCP	830 → 36122 [ACK] Seq=1 Ack=677 Win=490 Len=0

a

38.360022	NOKIA OT-1	ONOS Controller	TCP	830 → 48914 [PSH, ACK] Seq=1 Ack=677 Win=490 Len=148
38.364601	ONOS Controller	NOKIA OT-1	TCP	48914 → 830 [ACK] Seq=677 Ack=149 Win=1780 Len=0
38.365563	ONOS Controller	ADVA OLS Controller	HTTP	POST /restconf/data/tapi-common:context/tapi-connectivity:connectivity-context/ HTTP/1.1 (application/json)
38.365592	ONOS Controller	ADVA OLS Controller	HTTP	POST /restconf/data/tapi-common:context/tapi-connectivity:connectivity-context/ HTTP/1.1 (application/json)
38.365601	ONOS Controller	NOKIA OT-2	TCP	36122 → 830 [ACK] Seq=677 Ack=149 Win=1941 Len=0
38.365610	NOKIA OT-2	ONOS Controller	TCP	830 → 36122 [PSH, ACK] Seq=149 Ack=677 Win=490 Len=52

b

Fig. 3 Workflow traffic captures in the lab demonstration. (a) Topology discovery for the OLS and the Open Terminals, (b) TAPI Connectivity service for the OLS and configuration of the Open Terminals.

3.2 Work flow operations

There is an initial configuration providing to OSDNc is given the IP addresses and credentials of the open terminals and the OLS. With this information, OSDNc opens a NETCONF session over SSH to the terminal devices. Once the session has been established, transponder's capabilities are discovered by querying the device components, ports and interfaces, exposed by OpenConfig data model. Moreover, OSDNc employs TAPI interface to retrieve OLS topology and SIPs. In this work, the OLS exposes a node abstracting view of the network hiding optical components such as WSS, muxponders and amplifiers, but exposing the map of wavelengths available for media channels provisioning.

```

1 <config xmlns="urn:ietf:params:xml:ns:netconf:base:1.0">
2   <components xmlns="http://openconfig.net/yang/platform">
3     <component>
4       <name>OCH-1-2-1</name>
5       <oc-opt-term:optical-channel xmlns:oc-opt-term="
6         http://openconfig.net/yang/terminal-device">
7         <oc-opt-term:config>
8           <oc-opt-term:frequency>195300000</
9             oc-opt-term:frequency>
10        </oc-opt-term:config>
11      </oc-opt-term:optical-channel>
12    </component>
13  </components>
14 </config>

```

Fig. 4 Open Terminal configuration via OpenConfig

```

1 {"tapi-connectivity:output":{
2   "service":{
3     "connection":[
4       {
5         "connection-uuid":"3d71d84f-2714-413f-9652-3a61f7a7157b"
6       }
7     ],
8     "end-point":[
9       {
10        "local-id":"fbeb735f-9ef1-451d-924e-d3a1d70b37b7",
11        "service-interface-point":{
12          "service-interface-point-uuid":"dcf2a952-7d3f-464e-9d67-09567693ffeb"
13        }
14      },
15      {
16        "local-id":"eac8cd5-eda6-4142-a671-cd2d4eadf04a",
17        "service-interface-point":{
18          "service-interface-point-uuid":"1cde9ae1-4f56-4a30-be65-52afaa766cb1"
19        }
20      }
21    ],
22    "uuid":"e5bb0d5b-2e67-43b7-86f0-ec1b1ebs2c67"}}}

```

Fig. 5 ONOS TAPI Connectivity Service JSON reply.

Once OSDNc knows the topology interconnection between OLS and terminals information, the OSDNc can setup of an end-to-end connection between two client ports of the terminals exposed as SIPs through OSDNc TAPI NBI. To carry out such connectivity service, the OSDNc receives a T-API connectivity service request at the NBI RESTCONF interface. OSDNc breaks this request to trigger: (1) the TAPI phonic media channel connectivity service to configure the OLS segment; and two NETCONF configurations to modify the port state, power and frequency on the transponders line side (Fig.4). The transponder configuration is based on

OpenConfig optical-transport models. Finally, the OSDNc will reply to the OSS/BSS with the JSON shown in Fig.5.

4 Conclusion

Network disaggregation is a concept that is relevant for all the industry including network operators. Partially disaggregated network is an evolution from single vendor optical network infrastructures that requires integrated standard interfaces to move forward to such multi-vendor scenario. Moreover, it requires validating the physical impairments for each end-to-end optical signal that goes through the Open Line System. This work demonstrates for the first time, the provisioning of end-to-end photonic media channel connectivity service over a partially disaggregated scenario using TAPI 2.1.

5 Acknowledgements

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Commission for the H2020-ICT-2016-2 METRO-HAUL project (G.A. 761727).

6 References

- [1] E. Riccardi, et al.: 'An Operator's view on introduction of White Boxes in Optical Networks', in Journal of Lightwave Technology, August 2018, Vol. 36, Issue 15, pp. 3062-3072.
- [2] F. Pederzoli, et al.: 'SDN application-centric orchestration for multi-layer transport networks (Invited)', in proc. IEEE International Conf. on Transparent Optical Networks ICTON, paper Th.A4.2, Trento, Italy, July 2016.
- [3] Arturo Mayoral Lopez-de-Lerma, et al.: 'Multi-layer service provisioning over resilient Software-Defined partially disaggregated networks', OFC 2019, Tu3H. 6.
- [4] V. López, et al.: 'Control Plane Architectures for Elastic Optical Networks', J. Opt. Commun. Netw. **10**, A241-A249 2018.
- [5] Transport API, <https://github.com/OpenNetworkingFoundation/TAPI>, 2018
- [6] OpenConfig, <https://github.com/openconfig/public/tree/master/release/models/optical-transport>, 2018.
- [7] ONF, ONOS Whitepaper, <http://onosproject.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/Whitepaper-ONOS-final.pdf>, 2014